

PREVALENCE OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE USE AND ITS ASSOCIATED FACTORS IN DIABETES MELLITUS MANAGEMENT IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disease that causes disability and handicap with public health implications. The chronicity of the disease and its associated complications force patients to seek alternative means for permanent treatment or cure. This study assessed the prevalence and types of traditional medicine used and associated factors among adults with diabetes mellitus. This hospital-based cross-sectional study included 257 patients with DM who were undergoing routine clinics in two tertiary hospitals in Anambra State, Nigeria. An interviewer-administered questionnaire was used to collect patient-specific information. Ethical clearance was obtained, and data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 25.0. The mean age was 61.69 ± 8.20 years. Most respondents were Igbo (256, 99.6%) and lived in urban areas (181, 70.4%). Regarding education, 50.2% had secondary education, 99.6% were Christian (256), and 244 (94.9%) were married. The prevalence of traditional medicine use was 74.3%. The most commonly used TM type was bitter leaf (52.5%), followed by nazi (*Gongrenema latifolium*) at 47.1%. Family members (30.4%) and friends (28%) were the main influencers of the decision to use TM. Gender, age, diabetes duration, residence, occupation, education level, and presence of complications were significantly associated with TM use. The potency of TM is questionable; therefore, further studies involving its constituents, side effects, and beneficial effects are needed.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, prevalence, traditional medicine, associated factors, Anambra State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic disease condition characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, known as hyperglycemia, as a result of deficient insulin secretion from the pancreas or insulin resistance in target organs. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder of chronic hyperglycemia characterized by carbohydrate, protein, and fat metabolism disturbances resulting from absolute or relative insulin deficiency with organ system dysfunction (Ezuruike & Prieto, 2014). This can be due to insufficient endogenous insulin production by pancreatic beta cells (otherwise known as type-1 diabetes) or impaired insulin secretion or action (type-2 diabetes) (Kayarohanam, 2015). Hyperglycemia is a feature of diabetes. Hyperglycemia increases the risk of diabetes and associated complications, including heart attack, stroke, kidney disease, limb amputations, poor vision, and nerve damage (Gogoi et al., 2024). Hyperglycemia produces classical symptoms, including unusually large volumes of urine (polyuria), abnormal excessive thirst (polydipsia), and excessive hunger or increased appetite (Rezaei et al., 2015). Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a growing public health concern worldwide. In 2022, 14% of adults aged 18 years were living with diabetes, an increase from 7% in 1990. In 2022, more than half (59%) of adults aged 30 years and over living with diabetes were not taking medication for their diabetes in 2022 (World Health Organization 2024). The coverage of diabetes treatment was lowest in low- and middle-income countries (International Diabetes Federation, 2021). In Nigeria, the prevalence of diabetes is on the rise, with an estimated 3.7 million people living with the disease.⁶ According to the World Health Organization, Nigeria has one of the highest rates of diabetes in the region, and the number of cases is expected to continue to increase. As the burden of diabetes continues to rise, many individuals, especially in rural areas, often seek traditional medicine as an alternative or complementary approach to managing DM. Traditional medicine remains a key component of healthcare practices in Anambra State, a region in southeastern Nigeria, with herbal remedies and indigenous treatments widely used alongside conventional medical approaches. The management of diabetes may be influenced by many factors. These include medication adherence, health beliefs and cultural bias, health numeracy, access to health care and insurance issues, and socioeconomic status (Glasgow et al., 2013). Self-management practices in patients of African descent and other ethnic populations in developed countries were reviewed, and it was concluded that there was a lack of education, understanding, and communication at the patient level and cultural differences or cultural sensitivity at the provider level (Glasgow et al., 2013).

Traditional medicine refers to any form of health care delivery outside the confines of a hospital. Traditional medicine includes the use of herbal remedies, spiritual healing, and other forms of alternative medicine. The World Health Organization defines traditional medicine as "the sum total of the knowledge, skill, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement, or treatment of physical and mental illness" (Modibbo et al., 2024). Complementary and alternative medicines are terms that encompass health practices that are not integrated into a country's mainstream healthcare system and are often used interchangeably with traditional medicine (Modibbo et al., 2024).

Traditional medicine includes the use of herbs and plant-based preparations, known as herbal medicines, as well as practical procedures such as traditional bone setting (Modibbo et al., 2024). Although traditional medicine is

used in the management of diabetes, scientific evidence on its safety and effectiveness is lacking. Many traditional medicines have not been scientifically tested, and their use can be associated with adverse effects, interactions with modern medicines, and poor health outcomes. Therefore, it is important to review the effectiveness of targeted non-pharmacological interventions, such as traditional medicine use, on diabetes control among people in Anambra State, Nigeria. Such information is essential to establish the value, risks, and other factors associated with such strategies and to inform the design of future care strategies. The effectiveness of these interventions will be assessed based on their ability to reduce blood glucose levels and improve symptoms in the target population. The goal is to compare the interventions with control or usual care (Glasgow et al., 2013). Globally, 80%–85% of populations rely on these medicinal plants to manage diabetes using their extracts or their active components. Ethno-medicinal surveys indicate that more than 1200 plants have been used in traditional medicine systems because of their hypoglycemic properties (Kasole et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

A study shows that the burden of NCDs will increase by about three-quarters of all deaths and 60% of all diseases globally by 2020 (Animaw & Seyoum, 2017). Complications related to diabetes reduce a person's productivity with consequent loss of economic growth while placing a very heavy socio-economic and health care burden on the community and nation. Approximately 415 million and 14.2 million adults have diabetes worldwide and in Africa, respectively, and by 2045, it will rise to 700 million. Diabetes-related complications are a major cause of disability, reduced quality of life, and death (Abonyi et al., 2023). Many people believe in traditional ways of living, which influences their health-seeking behavior. Traditional medicines, which include normal foods and herbs, are used as the primary form of health care (Kasole et al., 2019). The International Diabetes Federation reported that approximately 75%–80% of people with diabetes die of to cardiovascular complications (Animaw & Seyoum, 2017). Diabetes mellitus and other non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are responsible for an increasing burden of diseases in developing countries. In Sub-Saharan Africa, NCDs are predicted to exceed infectious diseases by 2030 (Animaw & Seyoum, 2017). Sedentary lifestyles coupled with growing urbanization and processed diets are predicted to triple the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in the coming 25 years, including young populations (Animaw & Seyoum, 2017).

Nigeria, with an estimated 3.7 million people living with diabetes mellitus, is a growing cause for concern. Anambra is one of the most populous states in the country and is likely to have a significant number of people living with diabetes mellitus. Traditional medicine is an integral part of Nigerian culture, and many people living in Nigeria, especially in places like Anambra State, may be involved in using traditional medicine in the management of diabetes mellitus. This may be due to their cultural practices, dissatisfaction with conventional medicine use, or the fact that they have limited access to modern health facilities.

The World Health Organization's (WHO's) global report on traditional and complementary medicine 2019 used the term 'traditional and complementary medicine (T&CM)' to 'merge the terms traditional medicine and complementary medicine, encompassing products, practices, and practitioners' (Lee et al., 2022). Traditional medicine is the oldest medical practice in Nigeria (Kifle, 2021). Approximately 75%–80% of the world's population uses herbal medicines, mainly in developing countries, for primary health care because of their better acceptability with the human body and lesser side effects (Naja et al., 2014). Dissatisfaction with conventional

medicine is also a driver for the use of traditional medicine, and up to two-thirds of traditional medicine users do not disclose their use to conventional health practitioners (Lee et al., 2022). This raises concerns because there is evidence that the use of some traditional products and therapies is associated with adverse reactions including when, for example, traditional medicine products or preparations are used concurrently with conventional medicines (Lee et al., 2022). This study addressed knowledge gaps by providing data on the prevalence of traditional medicine use and the sociodemographic, cultural, and economic factors driving the health-seeking behavior for traditional medicine.

Conceptual Framework

Several factors influence self-care behaviors by patients in the treatment of their illnesses. Diabetic self-care practices, which may involve the use of traditional medicine either alone or in combination with conventional medicine, are influenced by dependent variables such as lifestyle factors (diet, exercise, and weight); socio-demographic factors (age, gender, marital status, monthly income, and level of education); and factors related to diabetes (years of suffering from diabetes, complications, and blood glucose self-monitoring). The use of traditional medicine is also influenced by the individual’s cultural beliefs, belief that these practices are more beneficial than the use of conventional medicines, and the feeling that these practices produce a kind of self-relief and self-efficacy (Weledegebriel et al. al., 2021). The relationships between the dependent and independent variables are shown in the figure below.

Fig 1. Conceptual Framework: Developed from the literature review

Methodology

Study Area

The study was conducted in Anambra State, which is located in the South-eastern region of the country and covers an area of 4,416 km². Anambra state nicknamed "Light of the Nation," was created on August 27, 1991, with Awka as its capital. Anambra State has 21 local government areas and recorded a population of 4,177,828 in 2006 according to the National Population Census. Its estimated population projection in 2025 is estimated to be 6,358,311, with a growth of approximately 6.8% since 2022, when the population was projected at 5,953,500. Anambra State has a rich cultural and religious heritage and an abundance of local herbs. In addition to the limited access and cost of modern medicine, the prevalent use of herbals in the management of ailments can be attributed. The new development of the Anambra state health care insurance scheme may improve health care outcomes. Notable tertiary health facilities as a feature of the State including: Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi North, and Psychiatric Hospital, Nawfia, Anambra State. Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Teaching Hospital, Amaku Awka South, Japan These hospitals offer comprehensive healthcare services, including specialty clinics (e.g., endocrinology, cardiology, neurology, and nephrology), diabetes management, traditional medicine research, surgery, and maternal health services.

Study Design

This hospital-based descriptive cross-sectional study

Study Population

The study population comprised all individuals diagnosed with DM.

Inclusion criteria

- Individuals diagnosed with type 1 or 2 diabetes and aged >18 years
- Individuals with DM who resided in Anambra State for at least 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria

- Participants with severe cognitive impairment or critical illness preventing participation.
- Pregnant women with gestational diabetes.

Determination of Sample Size

The study sample size was 257. This was calculated using the Cochran formula for determining sample size for descriptive studies.

Step 1,

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where,

n = Minimum sample size

z = Standard normal deviation, usually set at 1.96 for 95% confidence interval

p = proportion of the sample with the characteristic of interest. In this case, the prevalence of traditional medicine use was 34% (based on the prevalence of complementary and alternative medicine use among patients with diabetes mellitus in a tertiary institution in Southeast Nigeria).¹⁹

Using the above formula, approximately 345 was obtained.

Step 2, determination of the desired sample size

$$nf = n \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{n}}$$

$[1+(n/N)]$

nf = Minimum sample size of finite population (<10,000)

N= Estimated population size of 700 patients who attend a diabetic clinic.

nf = 345

$1+345/700$

$=231.101= 231$

Step 3,

A 10% non-response was considered, which is given as $nf= n \div 1-nw$

Where,

nf = final minimum sample size

nw = non-response rate

$nf= 231 \div 1- 0.1 = 231 \div 0.9 = 256.67$

Therefore, the final minimum sample size for the study was 257

A total of 257 respondents who met the inclusion criteria were interviewed.

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was used.

Stage 1: Using a stratified random sampling technique, Anambra State was divided into three senatorial zones (Central, South, and North Anambra) in Anambra State.

Stage 2: Simple random sampling was applied to select one LGA from each of the three senatorial zones.

Stage 3: A simple random sampling technique was also applied to select two hospital facilities from those selected in Stage 2.

Stage 4: Study participants were adults selected from the general outpatient clinic and endocrinology outpatient clinic. A systematic random sampling technique was used to select patients. From the sampling frame, the sampling interval $K = Xth /n$ population is obtained.

X is the estimated study population.

n is the total number of respondents.

Study Instrument

The study instrument, which comprised a semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire, was used to assess the prevalence and factors influencing the use of traditional medicine among patients with diabetes. The questionnaire, written in soft copy and written in English, was administered to respondents who met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaire had four sections:

Section A: Sociodemographic characteristics of the population

Section B: Prevalence of traditional medicine use among adults with DM.

Section C: Types of traditional medicine used among adults with DM.

Section D: Factors associated with the use of traditional medicine among adults with diabetes.

Data collection method

An interviewer-administered questionnaire was administered. It involved reading and explaining the questions to the respondents and ticking or circled their answers in the questionnaire.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 25.0 for accuracy and efficiency. Descriptive statistics summarized the sociodemographic characteristics and prevalence of the use of traditional medicine. The chi-square tests in SPSS were used to determine the associations between categorical variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Ethics Committee through the head of the Department of Community Medicine, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The reference is NAUTH/CS/66/VOL.17/VER.3/67/2025/51 which was dated 25th June, 2025.

Informed written consent was obtained from the respondents after explaining the purpose, objectives, and benefits of the research to them. The names of the respondents or any means of identification were omitted to ensure confidentiality, and they were informed that they were free to opt out at any stage without any penalty whatsoever. They were also assured of no harm in participation and that participation was entirely voluntary.

Results

A total of 257 adults participated in the study, and a 100% response rate was achieved. Among the 257 respondents, 44.7% were female (n = 115) and 55.3% were male (n = 142). The mean age was 61.69 ± 8.20 years. Most respondents were Igbo (256, 99.6%), predominantly Christian (256, 99.6%), lived in urban areas (181, 70.4%), had a secondary education (50.2%, 129), and were married (244, 94.9%). Most respondents were businesspeople/traders (45.9%, 118). More than half of the respondents earn ₦50,000–100,000 monthly (54.5%) For diabetes history, most (41.2%) were diagnosed for 6–10 years before the study. Regarding traditional medicine use, 33.5% used it for 1–5 years, 21% for 6–10 years, 14.8% for more than 10 years, 5.4% for less than a year, and 25.3% had never used it. Table 1

Table 1: Sociodemographic distribution of the respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	115	44.7
	Male	142	55.3
Age	<=45	5	1.9
	46-55	52	20.2
	56-65	101	39.3
	66-75	91	35.4
	>75	8	3.1
	Mean±STD	61.69±8.20	
Tribe	Igbo	256	99.6
	Yoruba	1	0.4
Place of residence	Rural	76	29.6
	Urban	181	70.4
The highest level of education attained	No formal education	4	1.6
	Primary	36	14
	Secondary	129	50.2

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	Tertiary	88	34.2
Religion	Christian	256	99.6
	Traditional	1	0.4
Marital status	Divorced	1	0.4
	Married	244	94.9
Occupations	Single	3	1.2
	Widowed	9	3.5
	Artisan	15	5.8
	Business/trader	118	45.9
	Civil servant	76	29.6
	Driver	2	0.8
	Farmer	15	5.8
	Retired	4	1.6
	Teacher	3	1.2
	Unemployed	24	9.3
Monthly income (₦)	Less than 50000	23	8.9
	50000-100000	140	54.5
	More than 100000	94	36.6
Duration since the diabetes diagnosis	Less than 1 year	4	1.6
	1-5 years	88	34.2
	6-10 years	106	41.2
	More than 10 years	59	23
Duration of use of traditional medicine	1-5 years	86	33.5
	6-10 years	54	21
	I have never used it.	65	25.3
	Less than 1 year	14	5.4
	More than 10 years	38	14.8

Most respondents (74.3%, 191) had used traditional medicine, whereas 25.7% (66%) had not. The main source of TM was home-prepared remedies (47.1%, 121), followed by local market vendors (16.7%, 43), herbalists (8.6%, 22), and online and religious institutions (0.8% each). Among those who combined medications, 66.1% (170) used both medications occasionally, 7% (18) used both medications regularly, and 25.7% (66) only used prescribed drugs. Most (88.3%, 227) patients used oral hypoglycemics, while 11.7% (30) used insulin. Table 2

Table 2: Traditional and prescribed medicine use among respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent age
History of the use of traditional medicine	Yes	191	74.3
	No	66	25.7
Primary source of traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	Herbalist/traditional healers	22	8.6
	Home-prepared remedies	122	47.9
	Local market vendors	43	16.7

	Online sources	2	0.8
	Religious institutions	2	0.8
Traditional and prescribed use diabetes medications together	I use it once a while	1	0.4
	No, I only use prescribed medication.	66	25.7
	No, I only use traditional medicine.	2	0.8
	Yes, regularly	18	7.0
	Yes, sometimes	170	66.1
Type of diabetes medication prescribed	Insulin	30	11.7
	Oral hypoglycemic drug	227	88.3

The study shows that 34.6% (89) of patients had temporarily stopped prescribed medicines for traditional ones; only one person (0.4%) had permanently stopped. Among those who used TM, 37.0% judged effectiveness by symptom reduction, 35% by improved well-being, and 28.8% by improved blood sugar levels. Nearly half of the respondents (49.8%) relied on recommendations. Complications were common (77.4%, 199), mainly blurring vision (67.3%), numbness (52.5%), and hypertension (49.8%). Other complications included leg ulcers (16.7%), kidney issues (14%), ED (11.7%), and stroke (5.4%). Table 3

Table 3: Effectiveness of traditional medicine and diabetes complications among respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Discontinuation of prescribed medication for traditional medicine	Yes, temporarily	89	34.6
	Yes, permanently	1	0.4
	No	167	65.0
How is the effectiveness of traditional medicine assessed?	I have never used it.	66	25.7
	Reduction of symptoms	95	37.0
	Improved blood sugar levels	74	28.8
	Improved personal well-being and energy levels	90	35.0
	Recommendations from others who have used it	128	49.8
Presence of complications of diabetes	It is not effective	0	0.0
	Yes	199	77.4
Complications experienced	No	58	22.6
	Blurring vision	173	67.3
	Leg ulcer	43	16.7
	Numbness	135	52.5
	Kidney problem	36	14.0
	Erectile dysfunction	30	11.7
	High blood	128	49.8
Stroke	14	5.4	

The bitter leaf was the most commonly used traditional remedy (52.5%, 135), followed by utazi (47.1%, 121), herbal mixtures (45.1%, 116), and ginger (23%, 59). 25.7% (66) never used any Recommenders were mainly

family members (30.4%, 78), friends (28%, 72), and fellow diabetics (6.6%, 17). Few patients received recommendations from media, medical journals, or traditional healers. Table 4

Table 4: Types and recommenders of traditional medicine among respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage	
Types of traditional medicine used	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7	
	Herbal mixtures/concoctions	116	45.1	
	Bitter leaf	135	52.5	
	Utazi	121	47.1	
	Honey	24	9.3	
	Spiritual healing	5	1.9	
	Moringa	74	28.8	
	Ginger	59	23.0	
	Bitter kola	48	18.7	
	Aloe vera	12	4.7	
	Supplements	30	11.7	
	Recommendation of traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
		Family member	78	30.4
Fellow patient with diabetes		17	6.6	
Friend		72	28.0	
Herbalist		12	4.7	
Media (television, radio, and telephone)		2	0.8	
Medical journal		1	0.4	
Self-decided		7	2.7	
Traditional healer		2	0.8	

It was found that 40.5% (104) of the patients prepared medicine themselves, 16% (41) bought it locally, and 7% (18) received it from their family. In terms of preparation methods, 67.7% (174) used decoctions, 45.1% (116) chewed them raw, 22.2% (57) drank herbal teas, and 5.4% (14) used capsules or tablets. Table 5

Table 5: Forms and methods of traditional medicine among respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Method of preparing or obtaining traditional medicine	I have never used the traditional	66	25.7
	Bought as a packaged product	6	2.3
	From a family member or relative	18	7.0
	A friend	3	1.2
	My wife and some friends	1	0.4
	My wife prepares them for me	1	0.4
	Prepare them myself at home	104	40.5
	Prescribed/made by a traditional healer	17	6.6
	Purchase or purchase from local vendors	41	16.0
	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7

Usual method of preparing or obtaining traditional medicines	Freshly boiled/decoction	174	67.7
	Powdered form	7	2.7
	Capsules/tablets	14	5.4
	Herbal teas	57	22.2
	Chewed or raw	116	45.1
	Topical application	6	2.3

The main reasons for using traditional medicine included belief in effectiveness (59.1%, 152), affordability (27.6%, 71), easy access (38.9%, 100), and recommendations (44.7%, 115). Influences included family (30.7%), friends (28%) and personal choice (12.1%). Only 13.6% (35) of the patients experienced side effects, mostly gastrointestinal issues (12.5%, 32), with some reports of hypoglycemia. 57.2% (147) were unaware of the potential side effects, and only 2.3% (6) proactively and personally researched on them. Table 6

Table 6: Reasons, influences, and adverse effects of traditional medicine use among respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Main reason for using traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	Belief in its effectiveness	152	59.1
	I can afford it.	71	27.6
	Cultural or family beliefs	27	10.5
	Dissatisfaction with the use of modern or conventional medicine	21	8.2
	Easy accessibility of these traditional medicines	100	38.9
	Recommendations from family and friends	115	44.7
Main influence on decision to use traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	Personal choice	31	12.1
	Family members	79	30.7
	Friends	72	28.0
	Herbalists	6	2.3
	Traditional healers	3	1.2
Experienced side effects	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	Yes	35	13.6
	None	156	60.0
Type of side effects experienced	Allergic reactions (rash, itching, swelling, diarrhea)	1	0.4
	Bitter taste	1	0.4
	Gastrointestinal issues (bitter taste, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea)	32	12.5
	Hypoglycemia (dizziness, sweating, fainting, and confusion)	4	1.6
Awareness of possible side effects before use	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	I was aware but did not take it seriously.	38	14.8
	No, I was not aware of it.	147	57.2
	Yes, I researched about it or was informed	6	2.3

The study showed that 37.4% (96) of the patients reported improved control, 7.8% (20) saw no change, and 29.2% (75) were unsure. Moreover, 68.5% (176) still visited hospitals while using traditional remedies Only 23.7% (61)

of patients disclosed traditional medicine use to health care providers; 50.2% (129) did not. Reasons for nondisclosure included: “I never thought about it” (12.8%, 33), fear of discouragement (17.1%, 44), or that doctors did not ask (13.2%, 34). Table 7

Table 7: Glycemic control while using traditional medicine and transparency about its use with healthcare providers

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Description of diabetes control using traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	Improved	96	37.4
	No change	20	7.8
	Not sure	75	29.2
Hospital visits while using TM	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	No	15	5.8
	Yes	176	68.5
Disclosure to health care providers about the use of traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	No	130	50.6
	Yes	61	23.7
Reason for not disclosing the use of traditional medicine	I have never used traditional medicine.	66	25.7
	No answer	53	20.6
	I never thought about it.	33	12.8
	I told my doctor	11	4.3
	My doctor did not ask me the following:	34	13.2
	My doctor will be angry	11	4.3
	My doctor will discourage me	44	17.1
Traditional medicine is safe	5	1.9	

Significant associations were found between the use of traditional medicine and gender ($p = 0.01$), age ($p = 0.04$), place of residence ($p = 0.03$), education level ($p < 0.01$), occupation ($p < 0.01$), diabetes duration ($p < 0.01$), and presence of complications ($p < 0.01$). It was found that 81.7% of females used traditional medicine compared with 67.6% of males. TM use increased with age and rural residence. Farmers and the unemployed had the highest usage rates (100% and 87.5%, respectively). Among patients diagnosed for over 10 years, 83.1% used traditional medicine. Complications were more common in users of traditional medicine (78.9%) than in non-users (56.9%).

Table 8: Association between traditional medicine use and sociodemographic variables

Variables	Categories	Yes	No	X ²	p-value
Gender	Female	94(81.7)	21(18.3)	6.59	0.01
	Male	96(67.6)	46(32.4)		
Age ranges	<=45	3(60)	2(40)	10.22	0.04
	46-55	31(59.6)	21(40.4)		
	56-65	76(75.2)	25(24.8)		
	66-75	72(79.1)	19(20.9)		
	>75	8(100)	0(0)		
Place of residence	Rural	63(82.9)	13(17.1)	4.50	0.03
	Urban	127(70.2)	54(29.8)		
The highest level of education attained	No formal education	3(75)	1(25)	13.69	<0.01
	Primary	31(86.1)	5(13.9)		
	Secondary	103(79.8)	26(20.2)		
	Tertiary	53(60.2)	35(39.8)		
Marital status	Divorced	0(0)	1(100)	5.53	0.14
	Married	182(74.6)	62(25.4)		
	Single	1(33.3)	2(66.7)		
	Widowed	7(77.8)	2(22.2)		
Occupations	Artisan	7(46.7)	8(53.3)	25.97	<0.01
	Business/trader	96(81.4)	22(18.6)		
	Civil servant	45(59.2)	31(40.8)		
	Driver	1(50)	1(50)		
	Farmer	15(100)	0(0)		
	Retired	3(75)	1(25)		
	Teacher	2(66.7)	1(33.3)		
	Unemployed	21(87.5)	3(12.5)		
Monthly income (₦)	Less than 50000	19(82.6)	4(17.4)	3.98	0.14
	50000-100000	108(77.1)	32(22.9)		
	More than 100000	63(67)	31(33)		
Duration since the diabetes diagnosis	Less than 1 year	1(25)	3(75)	17.58	<0.01
	1-5 years	54(61.4)	34(38.6)		
	6-10 years	86(81.1)	20(18.9)		
	More than 10 years	49(83.1)	10(16.9)		
Type of diabetes medication prescribed	Insulin	24(80)	6(20)	0.65	0.42
	Oral drug (hypoglycemic oral drug)	166(73.1)	61(26.9)		
Presence of complications of diabetes	Yes	157(78.9)	42(21.1)	11.28	<0.01
	No	33(56.9)	25(43.1)		

Discussion

The use of traditional medicine is fast assuming an important role in the management of DM. In this study, the prevalence of traditional medicine use among adult DM subjects was 74.3%. Abonyi et al. (2023) found a prevalence of 34% (Abonyi et.al. 2023). The prevalence was 67.3% in another multicenter study in Lagos, Nigeria (Amaeze et al., 2018). These differences in prevalence could have been due to regional and tribal differences in the use of traditional medicine. The prevalence of traditional medicine use in Africa is high, with an estimated prevalence of 80% (Abonyi et al., 2023). It was found to be 73.7% in Ethiopia (Weledegebriel et.al. 2021) and 92.1% in Zambia (Nangandu et.a., 2022). The reported prevalence rate of traditional medicine use among patients with DM was 38% in Lebanon (Naja et al., 2014), 40.7% in India (Kesavadev et al., 2023) and 88.4% in Iran (Sheikhrabori et al., 2016). The higher use of traditional medicine in our study might be due to the non-availability of regular and free antidiabetic medication in the public health system, lack of perceived side effects from the type of traditional medicine used, variation in cultural perceptions of traditional medicine use, and acceptability of traditional medicine. In addition, poor adherence to conventional medicine by patients with diabetes in the study area could be another reason for the higher use of traditional medicine. Variations in the use of traditional medicine by geographic region could contribute to differences in the accessibility and availability of modern medicine and sociocultural perceptions of the use of traditional medicine among participants. In addition, the differences in the definitions of traditional medicine/CAM AND study designs could have also been attributed to the variation in the prevalence of traditional medicine use by patients with diabetes in these countries.

In this study, the most commonly used traditional medicine was bitter leaf (*Vernonia amygdalina*), followed by Utazi (*Gongronema latifolium*) and herbal mixtures/concoctions. Abonyi et al. (2023) found that the most commonly used traditional medicine was bitter leaf (*Vernonia amygdalina*), bitter kola (*Garcinia kola*), and scent leaf (African basil). Amaeze et al. (2023) also found that bitter leaf was the most commonly used traditional medicine followed by *Moringa oleifera* seeds and herbal mixtures (Abonyi et.al.,2023). Nigerian researchers have reported a lowering of blood glucose in diabetic rats when they were fed with bitter leaf, and this lowering of glucose was comparable to that recorded in diabetic rats who were administered with oral glucose-lowering agents (Radwan et al., 2021). Many patients with DM in Nigeria believe that the bitterness in bitter leaf, utah, herbal mixtures, or any preparations containing bitter would dilute the sweetness of the sugar in their blood. This could explain why they are some of the most commonly used CAM in this study, as well as in other studies in Nigeria. In this study, family members were the most frequently reported source of recommendation about the use of traditional medicine, followed by friends and fellow patients with diabetes who also used traditional medicine, while few received recommendations from media, medical journals, and traditional healers. This finding was almost consistent with that of a similar study by Abonyi et al., where two-thirds of the participants were introduced by friends and a quarter by family members (Radwan et al., 2021). However, a study conducted in Ethiopia revealed that the majority of the traditional medicine users were encouraged or referred to use traditional medicine by traditional healers followed by family and friends (Weledegebriel et al., 2021).

The results of this study are consistent with those of a similar study by Amaeze *et al.*, in which the most widely reported reason for the use of traditional medicine was their belief in its effectiveness. This is because the users of these traditional medicines have a feeling that they are safe and therefore believe in their effectiveness. In

Nigeria and most African countries, traditional medicine, especially herbal medicines, are generally perceived and widely advertised as being devoid of any side effects because they are “natural.” This resonates with the general belief that herbal remedies are natural and therefore risk-free. These beliefs could also be culturally rooted. However, some clinical reports have shown that this belief is erroneous. A few examples of herbal medications and drug interactions include the interaction of *Matricaria recutita* (Chamomile) with warfarin, which results in over-coagulation. *Allium sativum* (Garlic) altered the pharmacokinetics of paracetamol and caused hypoglycemia when co-administered with chlorpropamide (Abonyi et al., 2023).

The majority of subjects using traditional medicine did not disclose their use to their healthcare practitioners (HCP). This high rate of non-disclosure was also found in previous studies (Abonyi et al., 2023; Radwan et al., 2021). The most common reason for the non-disclosure in this study was that they never thought about it. Other reported reasons were fear of discouragement and that the doctor did not ask. This underscores the importance of holistic communication while interacting with patients during assessment. It is known that medicinal plants reduce blood glucose levels through biochemical mechanisms such as restitution of pancreatic β -cell function, improvement in insulin sensitivity by receptors, stimulation of insulin secretion, inhibition of liver gluconeogenesis, enhanced glucose absorption, and inhibition of G-6-Pase, α -amylase, and α -glucosidase activities (Radwan et al., 2021). However, the use of CAM is fraught with many problems, including drug-to-drug interactions, side effects, dosing, limited knowledge of the various constituents of each CAM, and the possibility of further complications in the subjects taking them (Radwan et al., 2021). This problem is compounded by Nigeria’s weak regulation of the production, distribution, and use of non-orthodox remedies. The predictors of herbal medicine use in our study were gender, age, residence, education level, occupation, diabetes duration, and the presence of complications. Increasing age has been reported to be associated with the use of alternative medicine in patients with diabetes (Nangandu et al., 2022; Kesavadev et al., 2021; Weledegebriel et al., 2021). This can be explained by the presence of multiple disease states and comorbidities in the older adults and the consequent desire to seek various treatment options to better control their health condition. Our study showed that female patients were the predominant traditional medicine users. This report was different from the findings by Radwan *et al.*, and this can be due to the fact that females tend to seek urgent care for any disease condition. Other studies have suggested that gender is not a significant predictor of traditional medicine use among patients with diabetes mellitus (Abonyi et al., 2023; Amaeze et al., 2018). Educational level positively influenced herbal medicine use in our respondents, which was similar to the findings of Amaeze et al. This may reflect better knowledge and awareness of traditional medicine due to higher literacy rates among those with formal education. Our results also support previous reports on the association between a longer duration of diabetes and CAM use (Abonyi et al., 2023; Amaeze et al., 2018). The presence of a diabetic complication indicates the severity of diabetes and the increased need for more treatment alternatives, which may encourage the use of CAM as a second option. The reason for this may be that older people who are more likely to have had DM for a longer period of time may be disenchanted with the incurable nature of their condition or may have experienced orthodox medications’ side effects. In this study, rural dwellers were more likely to use traditional medicine than urban dwellers. The reason for this may be that rural dwellers have more access to herbs than subjects who live in urban

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areas. Furthermore, the dearth of health care professionals (medical specialists, pharmacists, and qualified nurses) in rural communities in Nigeria encourages the use of traditional medicine.

Conclusion

The prevalence of traditional medicine use among adults with diabetes mellitus in Anambra state, Nigeria, was 74.3%. Most subjects used traditional medicine concurrently with conventional medicine, and most of them were introduced to them by their family members and friends. Most health care professionals do not make enquiries on their subjects' use of traditional medicine.

Recommendations

Research should be conducted on the potential and benefits of medicinal plants by the government and various organizations to explore the different mechanisms of favorable metabolic effects of these traditional medicines. It is noteworthy that metformin, the first choice in the treatment of type 2 diabetes, originated from the plant *Galega officinalis* (French lilac or goats' rue) and was once considered a CAM. Health care providers, particularly physicians, should routinely inquire and discuss the use of traditional medicine with patients in a caring and unbiased manner. Awareness programs targeting health care providers and patients on the use of CAM should be created to educate them on the various aspects of this treatment modality. This will ensure that the group with HCP are knowledgeable enough to discuss the CAM therapies that the patients are using or thinking of using to communicate with them more effectively. Guidelines should be created and regulatory bodies empowered to check the use of CAM. Further research in assessing the side effects experienced by subjects who use traditional medicine could be conducted by future researchers.

Limitations

The limitations of the study include the following: The study is cross-sectional and depends on self-reported assessment, and under-reporting is more likely to occur. Data collection was performed in the hospital setting; hence, participants could experience the social desirability bias, and their responses were likely converted to satisfy their health care professionals. Thus, the exact prevalence may not have been truly captured. Only patients who attended hospitals were surveyed, and individuals who were either undiagnosed or patients who received care outside the hospital were not accounted for. Private health facilities were not included in our study; thus, generalization of the study is limited.

Further Research

Longitudinal and mixed-method studies are needed to explore further details and comprehensiveness of the use of traditional medicines among patients with diabetes. Such research would provide evidence-based strategies for program design and implementation in similar contexts. The study can be expanded to include more facilities in different states of Nigeria to obtain a broader view of the subject matter.

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